

Computer Vision Syndrome in Students of a Medical School in Colombia. A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: The incidence of computer vision syndrome (CVS) is rising due to the use of digital platforms. There have been reports of higher rates of CVS in medical students. Thus, we decided to describe this syndrome in medical students of the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana.

Methods: The computer-vision symptom scale (CVSS17) was applied to 112 medical students from the seventh to the tenth semester. We estimated the prevalence, and bivariate analysis was done to compare the proportions, screen time, and score between groups.

Results: 63.39 % of students reported having myopia, 55.35 % astigmatism, 10.71 % hyperopia, and 14.28 % dry eye. The median time of screen exposure was 8 hours (IQR = 4), CVSS17 scores 34.5 (IQR = 9.5), internal symptomatic factor 12 (IQR 3), and external symptomatic factor 23 (IQR 7). The overall prevalence of CVS was 41.07 %. The bivariate analysis comparing both CVS with non-CVS showed a similar distribution of the analyzed variables. Common ocular symptoms were eyelid heaviness (98.2 %), eye strain (93.8 %) and eye congestion (93.8 %), visual symptoms were accommodative dysfunction (61.6 %), blurry vision (55.4 %) and accommodation spasm (52.7 %).

Discussion: Long shifts, academic sessions, work, presentations, tests, internet, and smartphone misuse are hypotheses thought to influence the screen time of medical students. The external symptoms were more frequent and those are more susceptible to interventions. We propose a health promotion and prevention of disease strategy.

Conclusion: It is important to encourage medical student's screen time breaks, increase blinking frequency, monitor the electronic use time "detoxing method", and establish adequate light in the environment, along with adequate or comfortable postures

Keywords: Computer vision syndrome, medical students, visual health, smartphone, electronic devices

Abbreviations: Computer vision syndrome (CVS), visual fatigue (VF), digital eye strain (DES), Computer vision syndrome scale (CVSS17)

Introduction:

Nowadays it is nearly impossible to stay away from screens, given the robust advances in technology. Electronic devices are relevant for work and academic purposes, as well as for leisure and entertainment (1). Nevertheless, there is an increasing concern about excessive screen time and the development of a variety of ocular symptoms, collectively referred to as computer vision syndrome (CVS) (2,3). The terms visual fatigue (VF), and digital eye strain (DES) are also known for this condition. Similar but not quite the same is visual stress which occurs when there is a dysfunction of visual processing leading to progressive visual discomfort while reading (4).

Depending on the symptoms, CVS can be categorized into three different groups (5). First, and the most known are the visual and asthenopic symptoms that include blurred or double vision, difficulty, slowness focusing objects, eye strain, tired eyes, convergence, and accommodation insufficiency (2). There is a higher incidence of these symptoms in individuals with a pre-existent refractive error, especially if glasses are not used in front of a screen (6). Second, ocular symptoms can appear due to prolonged screen focus, a decrease in the blinking frequency, and deficient corneal lubrication, resulting in dry eye, itching, burning, irritation, redness, heaviness, and tearing in attempt to rewet the surface of the eye (2). Last but not least, extraocular symptoms such as headaches, back, neck, and shoulder pain can arise due to inadequate or forced postures (7).

Reading on a digital screen requires more effort compared to reading in paper-based texts. When a letter is displayed in a video terminal their borders are not as precise or sharply defined, the level of contrast of the letters to the background is reduced, there can be glare and reflections on the screen, and in some cases the screen movement makes viewing difficult (3). This is why the daily screen time exposure is the most important risk factor for developing CVS (2). Other known risk factors include increasing age (due to diminished corneal lubrication), reduced blink rate, increasing video-terminal exposure, medications (can contribute to corneal drying), the cosmetic use of creams and makeup (can block the oil-secreting meibomian glands), the inconsistent use of glasses, the low frequency of breaks, the use of contact lenses, the inadequate posture, and environmental conditions such as the display quality, the temperature, humidity, lighting, dry air, ventilation fans, airborne dust, and building contaminants (3,6).

Different studies have evaluated the frequency of ocular and visual symptoms in computer users, indicating that 64 to 90 % of users can experience CVS (8–10). Those symptoms are influenced by the visual demand and task. In fact, individuals exposed to more than 4 hours working in front of a computer experience a higher incidence of both, ocular and visual symptoms (11).

This problematic is raising due to what has caused the COVID-19 in the last two years. The pandemic came with a series of policies that increased our time at home, imposing digital platforms as the only means for people to maintain social and working activities (12). As a result, the use of digital platforms and the overall incidence of CVS has increased substantially (13–18). According to recent data, 93.6% of individuals increased their screen time during the lockdown time, with an average increase of 4.8 hours (17). Also, a prevalence of CVS as high as 50.6 % in students attending online classes has been reported (13).

The most common refractory disorder that can arise or progress due to screen exposure is myopia, also known as nearsightedness (19,20). The prevalence of myopia has increased in the last decades, especially in the Asiatic countries (21). According to the MIOPUR Colombian Study (Determination of the Prevalence of Myopia and its Association with Environmental Influences in Urban and Rural Colombian Population), 12.9 % of the sample reported having myopia, and the prevalence increased during childhood, and adolescence, and was higher in middle-aged adults (22), coincidentally the population with the highest exposure to electronic media. In medical students, there are some reports outlining that refractory disorders can progress or can become incident during their study period (23,24). Also, in a Mexican cohort that included 406 medical students a higher prevalence of myopia compared to other demographic groups was identified (25). Furthermore, a study on medical students of five universities in Egypt reported that CVS was significantly associated with increased screen-hours with an OR of 2.48 for 2 screen hours daily and OR of 1.69 for 3 screen hours daily (26).

Given the increasing visual and ocular symptoms in the current technology era, the higher prevalence of this disorder, and the higher prevalence in medical students, this study aimed to describe the computer visual syndrome in medical students of the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana.

Methods

This is a cross-sectional study that included 112 medical students from the seventh to tenth semesters. A convenience sampling was carried out; students enrolled in each semester who wished to take the survey were included for the data recollection. A call was made through the faculty's social networks and the WhatsApp groups of each of the semesters. A “snowball sampling” was used, where each participant was encouraged to invite friends from their online social network. Students who did not wish to answer the survey, and those who did not finish the survey were excluded from the analysis.

We applied a survey with three different sections (See Annex 1). The first section included the informed consent of the study; the second section included different

sociodemographic variables such as semester, sex, and age, along with self-report of ophthalmologic history and the screen time exposure, and the third section included the previously validated computer-vision symptom scale (CVSS17). This instrument has been developed to measure ocular and visual symptoms that arise following screen exposition (27). It is composed of 17 items; the total score ranges from 17 to 53, and it can be classified into six different levels (level 1 from 17 to 22, level 2 from 23 to 28, level 3 from 29 to 35, level 4 from 36 to 42, level 5 from 43 to 49, and level 6 from 50 to 53). The score has two subtotals, the internal and external symptomatic factor, that reflect the visual and ocular symptoms, respectively. There were no visual tests, or a clinical assessment protocol used to document the symptoms or refractory disorders, all variables were self-reported according to what people answered in the survey.

As a recollection tool used Microsoft Forms®. The data on the surveys completed by each person was tabulated and analyzed using Microsoft Office Excel 16 and Stata 16. We used absolute and relative frequencies for qualitative variables and measures of central tendency (averages or medians) and dispersion (standard deviation) for quantitative variables. Statistical normality tests (Skew test, Shapiro Wilk) were used to analyze the normality of the distribution of quantitative variables. Two groups were created, those with and without CVS. CVS was defined if the score was equal to or higher than 36, which includes levels 4 to 6 on the symptomatic scale. A bivariate analysis was performed to compare the proportions (using the Chi2 test), averages (using t test), and medians (using Mann-Witney U test).

Results:

One hundred and twelve medical students answered the survey (table 1). 32.14 % were males and 67.86 % were females. There were 29 students from seventh (25.90%), 26 from eight (23.21%), 14 from ninth (12.50%), and 43 from tenth (38.39%) semester respectively. The median age was 21 (IQR =1) and the mean age was 21.35 (SD 1.16). In terms of ophthalmic history, 63.39 % of students reported having myopia, 55.35 % astigmatism, 10.71 % hyperopia, 14.28 % dry eye, 2.68 % conjunctival disease, and 1.7 % corneal disease.

Table 1. Demographics, Ophthalmic History and Measurements

Variable	Category	Total (n=112)	No-CVS (n = 66 58.93 %)	CVS (n = 46 41.07 %)	Bivariate analysis
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	p-value
Sex	Male	36 (32.14)	25 (37.88)	11 (23.91)	0.119
	Female	76 (67.86)	41 (62.12)	35 (76.09)	
Semester	7 th	29 (25.89)	12 (18.18)	17 (36.96)	0.038
	8 th	26 (23.21)	15 (22.73)	11 (23.91)	
	9 th	14 (12.50)	7 (10.61)	7 (15.22)	
	10 th	43 (38.39)	32 (48.48)	11 (23.91)	
Age*					

	Median (IQR)	21 (1)	21 (1)	20 (2)	0.016
	Mean (SD)	21.35 (1.16)	21.53 (1.25)	21.10 (0.99)	0.06
Eye Disorders					
	Myopia	71 (63.39)	41 (62.12)	30 (65.21)	0.311
	Astigmatism	62 (55.35)	33 (50.00)	29 (63.04)	0.599
	Hyperopia	12 (10.71)	8 (12.12)	4 (8.70)	0.385
	Dry eye	16 (14.28)	7 (10.60)	9 (19.57)	0.315
	Conjunctival Diseases	3 (2.68)	0 (0.00)	3 (6.52)	0.051
	Corneal diseases	2 (1.7)	1 (1.51)	1 (2.17)	0.884
	Other	3 (2.68)	1 (1.51)	2 (4.34)	0.266
	Total	89 (79.4)	49 (74.24)	40 (86.96)	0.083
Screen Hours*					
	Median (IQR)	8 (4)	8 (4)	8 (4)	0.86
	Mean (SD)	7.94 (3.2)	7.83 (3.18)	8.10 (3.26)	0.65
CVSS-17 score*					
	Median (IQR)	34.5 (9.5)	31 (6)	42 (6)	< 0.001
	Mean (SD)	35.22 (6.92)	30.51 (3.94)	41.97 (4.057)	< 0.001
Internal symptomatic factor*					
	Median (IQR)	12 (3)	10 (2)	14 (3)	< 0.001
	Mean (SD)	11.75 (2.94)	9.97 (1.65)	14.32 (2.45)	< 0.001
External symptomatic factor*					
	Median (IQR)	23 (7)	21 (4)	28 (5)	< 0.001
	Mean (SD)	23.46 (4.57)	20.54 (2.49)	27.65 (3.22)	< 0.001

*Quantitative variables (central tendency and dispersion measurements are provided)

The median time of screen exposure was 8 hours (IQR = 4), and the mean was 7.94 hours (SD 3.2, 95 % CI 7.34-8.54). Among them, 17.86 % (n=20) reported spending more than 12 hours in front of a screen, 32.83 % (n=39) 8 to 11 hours, 17.86 % (n = 20) 4 to 7 hours, and 2.68 % (n=3) less than 4 hours (see figure 1).

Figure 1. Daily hours medical students spend in front of a screen

CVSS17 scores were mean 35.22, median 34.5, minimum 20, maximum 51, the interquartile range was 9.5 and their standard deviation was 6.92. The 95% confidence interval for the population mean was 33.92 to 36.51. The internal symptomatic factor median and mean were 12 (IQR 3) and 11.75 (SD 2.94, 95 % CI 11.20-12.31), and the external symptomatic factor median and mean were 23 (IQR 7) and 23.46 (SD 4.58, 95 % CI 22.60-24.31) respectively. Most individuals were categorized as being in level 3 (n = 47, 41.96 %), 5 were categorized in level 1 (4.46 %), 12 in level 2 (10.71%), 26 in level 4 (23.21%), 17 in level 5 (15.18%) and 5 in level 6 (4.46 %) (See figure 2).

Figure 2. Categorization according to the CVSS-17 total score

Forty-six students met the established criteria for CVS, for an overall prevalence of 41.07 %. The bivariate analysis comparing CVS students with non-CVS students showed a similar distribution of age and sex. The frequency of refractory disorders was similar in both groups, with myopia (62.12 % vs 65.21, p-value 0.311), astigmatism (63.04 % vs 50 %, p-value 0.599) and hyperopia (8.7 % vs 12.12, p-value 0.385). Nevertheless, a slight difference was seen in dry eye in the CVS group (19.57 % vs 10.60 %, p-value 0.315). Also, the three individuals with conjunctival disorder (6.52%) were categorized as having CVS. There were no differences in terms of screen time of both groups (p = 0.65).

Regarding symptoms, the most common visual symptom was accommodative dysfunction (61.6 %), followed by blurry vision (55.4 %), accommodation spasm (52.7%), photophobia (50 %), convergence insufficiency (40.2 %) and diplopia (19.7 %). In terms of ocular or external symptoms eyelid heaviness (98.2 %) was the most common symptom, followed by eye strain (93.8%), eye congestion (93.8%), eye sting (89.3%),

increased need to blink (88.4%), eye pain (83.9%), eye itching (79.5%), visual fatigue (72.3%), dry eye (58.9%), conjunctival hyperemia (52.7%) and epiphora (48.2%).

Discussion:

The main purpose of the following study was to characterize the self-reported refractory disorders, and the ocular and visual symptoms frequently encountered by medical students of the advanced semesters of Pontificia Universidad Javeriana exposed to screens. In addition, as a secondary purpose, we evaluated the daily screen hours, and CVS prevalence among the medical students included in our sample, nevertheless a comprehensive ophthalmologic evaluation is required to document the presence of this condition.

The most common refractory disorder reported in our sample was myopia (63.39 %), followed by astigmatism (55.35 %) and hyperopia (10.71 %). This data is in the same line as what has been reported in other Latin American medical student cohorts. A study in Mexico that included 300 students found a prevalence of myopia of 68.7% (25), in the Dominican Republic 31.9% of 116 medical students were identified with myopia (28), and in Ecuador, 26.67% out of 180 students had myopia (29). These values are relatively lower than what has been reported in other Asian countries such as China (84.1%), Singapore (89.8%), and Taiwan (95.8%) (23,30,31).

Another reported symptom that was relatively frequent was dry eye. This has also been reported in similar cohorts. In a cross-sectional study that included 844 medical students of Peru 70.9 % reported having dry eye (32). In Brazil, 34.4% of undergraduate students met the Ocular Surface Disease Index (OSDI) scores for dry eye (33). The overall increase in this condition has been attributed to the improper use university students give to the internet and smartphones, without taking the required breaks and blinking that is needed for corneal lubrication (34,35). In fact, a Colombian sample that included 595 university students of Ibague reported improper use of the internet in 12 % of individuals (36). Moreover, there are reports outlining that eye dryness can be a reflection of psychological stress in medical students (32,37).

We identified that 41.07 % of students had symptoms suggestive of moderate CVS, but 98.2 % of students reported having at least one symptom being the most frequent eyelid heaviness. In India, 82.3% of students experienced one or more symptoms of digital vision syndrome during the intensive lockdown of COVID-19 (38). Also, accommodative asthenopia has been reported in medical students from Egypt, 84.8 to 87.9% of students had complaints included in the CVS (26,39). In another study, 95 % of medical students reported having at least one symptom of CVS during their study time (40). Another report outlines that medical students were 1.6 times to suffer from computer vision syndrome (95% CI 1.22, 2.24) (41). As seen in the following studies the variety of symptoms included in the CVS are commonly reported in medical students, a hypothesis of smartphone misuse has been proposed (39), but this finding needs to be supported by further studies.

The median self-reported screen time was eight hours, and most students spent eight or more hours in front of a screen. Similar results were seen in a Peruvian sample where most students spent six or more hours in front of a screen (32). Additionally, a Turkish study found out that most university students spent four or more hours/daily on screens (42). These findings can be correlated with the long shifts that clinical students are exposed during the clinical practices, also the academic sessions, the works, presentations, and tests, that are commonly done using electronic platforms. In fact, in a Saudi Arabian sample, the most significant related factors for computer use that increased the incidence of dry eye were the duration of study, a short distance from the screen, and high brightness in the screen (40).

We found out that the ocular or external symptoms were far more common than visual or internal symptoms, and among them, eyelid heaviness was the most common complaint, followed by eye strain and visual congestion. This is similar to a Romanian cohort of 402 medical students that reported tired eyes/eye strain in 86.1%, burning eyes in 46.8%, migraines/headaches in 46.8%, red-swollen eyes in 43%, photophobia in 41.8%, temporary blurred vision in 35.4%, and eyelid spasms in 32.9% of students (43). Other studies report that a common symptom that students experience after prolonged time in front of a screen is headache, nevertheless, this was not evaluated in our survey (39,41). In the reviewed articles we found out that external symptoms are those that respond the most to preventive strategies making it an excellent point for intervention (2,6,44).

Many of the mentioned signs and symptoms overlap of those seen in visual stress. In visual stress reading difficulties as blurring, movement, change in size of letters, along with light sensitivity, and headaches arise from exposure to disturbing visual patterns (45). This is manifested in the school environment, where greater attention and visual efficiency are required from the student, in addition to constant contact with printed material (46–48). The contrast of black letters on white paper, the quality of the print and the glare caused by the light shining on the paper are factors that can lead people with visual stress to make a greater effort to maintain the reading activity (48). Therefore, visual-perceptual distortions are often reported, such as blurred letters, vibration, pulsation, change in position, and movement, causing reading problems (dyslexia), and other learning difficulties (47,49,50).

Our bivariate analysis did not show differences in terms of ophthalmologic history in individuals that met the criteria of CVS and those who did not. Nevertheless, there are old reports stating that individuals with myopia can present a shift of -0.12 D after a working period in front of a screen, which is usually transient (51,52) leading to blurred vision. According to the most recent systematic review and meta-analysis smartphones in combination with computer screen exposure was significantly associated with the development of myopia (OR = 1.77, 95 % CI 1.28–2.45]; $I^2=87%$) (53). The increase in the refractory disturbance along with the wrong eyeglass prescription increases the visual symptoms while exposed to screens. The difference seen with our data can be attributed to the high prevalence of this disorder in medical students, but this does not rule out the presence of refractory disorder as a risk factor for developing visual symptoms.

Furthermore, our bivariate analysis did not show differences in terms of screen time in individuals with and without CVS. Even so, there are reports that state a direct relationship between screen time and the development of CVS (26). Tawil et. al reports that the use of electronic devices for more than 5 h increases the likelihood of CVS by 1.52 times (95% CI 1.07, 2.16) (41). We hypothesize that there was no difference in both groups given that most of the individuals were exposed to similar screen time since they have similar academic duties.

Given the high prevalence of this disorder in the studied population we decided to share with medical students the three main groups of strategies that can be done to prevent the development of CVS. The first and most important is the implementation of work breaks. Studies have shown that working for more than 4 hours at a computer screen has a significant association with asthenopia (2), given this information, it is recommended to take frequent breaks to restore and relax the accommodative system thus reducing eye strain. In Taiwanese schools, students are encouraged to rest their eyes for 10 minutes after 30-40 minutes of educational screen time (54). Another approach is to implement the 20-20-20 rule, which states that every 20 minutes try to focus on an object that is about 20 feet away for a full 20 seconds (3). Second, a digital detox method can be used to encourage healthy digital device habits, using digital applications to consciously monitor device usage, and reminding users to disconnect after a specific time from the digital world (54). Third, is the implementation of adequate lighting in the environment in order to maintain the same level of brightness in the users visual field (2). Furthermore, when people are looking at screens, they tend to blink less than usual which affects convergence so they can't focus on the screen (55).

To share the following strategies with the medical students of the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana we sent an infographic poster through the faculty social networks (See Annex 5). In the students that completed the survey, we gave feedback (via e-mail) according to their overall score, their external and internal symptomatic factor. If they were classified as being level 1 or 2, they were recommended to try the preventive strategies since they are having mild symptoms that can lead to the development of CVS in the future. For students being in levels 3-4, we informed them that they had symptoms suggestive of CVS and that it is important to apply the lifestyles mentioned to decrease the symptom frequency and progression. Nevertheless, if symptoms continue to progress, we recommended to seek help from a physician. Finally, for students being in levels 5-6, besides telling them that they had symptoms highly suggestive of CVS, we encouraged them to seek help from an ophthalmologist.

We consider our approach a health promotion, primary, secondary, and tertiary prevention strategies. Health promotion since we are stimulating at a population level of medical students with no ocular or visual symptoms and minimal risk factors to take a healthier style while being in front of a screen. Primary prevention, since high risk individuals with minimal symptoms not classified as having CVS, were provided the information to prevent this disorder. Secondary prevention, since we screened students for CVS, even if they were not aware of the symptoms and we highlighted the importance of taking the mentioned strategies. And finally, tertiary prevention since individuals with

significant internal or external symptoms (categorized as having a CVS level 5 to 6) were encouraged to go to an ophthalmologist to assess if some adjustments can be done to the eye-glass prescription to improve the visual symptoms, or an eye drop that can be given to improve the ocular symptoms, reducing the frequency and progression of these complains.

This study has some limitations, first, we are establishing a diagnosis of CVS based on a self-reported questionnaire, but the gold standard is by performing an extensive ophthalmologic evaluation. In the ideal scenario, each eye should be assessed independently as binocular vision can mask some visual disorders. Second, this is a cross-sectional study so causality cannot be established, nevertheless, no association between refractory disorders, screen time, and CVS was identified. Third, the included sample was small for epidemiologic purposes, and represented less than half of the individuals enrolled in each semester, so our data might not reflect the whole sample of medical students, even so similar data has been reported. The strength of this study was the use of validated questionnaire to screen for a common condition among medical students, also we propose a health promotion and prevention of disease strategy.

Conclusion:

Refractory disorders are common in medical students, with myopia being the most prevalent condition. This is the first study evaluating the CVS in a small population of medical students of Colombia. We found that CVS is common in medical students during their clinical practice, 41.07 % had symptoms suggestive of CVS, most of the students were classified as being at level 3 in the CVSS-17 questionnaire. Since the mean screen time in our sample was greater than 4 hours it is important to encourage in medical students screen time breaks, increase blinking frequency, monitor the electronic use time “detoxing method”, and establish adequate light in the environment, along with adequate or comfortable postures. The previously mentioned strategies have shown to decrease the incidence and prevalence of this disorder. Further studies are required to establish the association between screen time and CVS, the overall incidence of CVS in students exposed to screens, and the association with refractory disorders and with reading difficulties.

Ethical approval and consent to participate

According to resolution 8430 of 1993 of the Colombian Ministry of Health, this work is classified in the category "research without risk". It also respects the fundamental ethical principles in accordance with the Nuremberg Code, the Declaration of Helsinki, and the Belmont Report. The patients/ participants provided their written informed consent to participate in this study.

Competing interest disclaimer:

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be constructed as a potential conflict. Also, the research was not funded by any company, it was conducted by personal efforts of the authors.

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